

Muñoz *et al.* Supplemental Table.

Oligonucleotides used in this work. Boldface indicates changes introduced to create specific mutations. Restriction sites (either present in the native sequence or artificially created) are underlined.

Name	Sequence
5'HAL3EcoRI	G <u>GG</u> AATTCATGACTGCCGTGCGCTCTACT
3'HAL3XhoI	CACGCT <u>CGAG</u> CATAGACTATTTATTGATGC
5'HAL3BamHI	ATTT <u>GGATCC</u> CAGACTACCT
3'HAL3HpaI	ACGATTTT <u>GTTAA</u> CAATCTC
5'HAL3His378Ala	CTGTA <u>CTT</u> GCT TATAGAACTACGTCGCTG
3'HAL3His378Ala	GTTCTATAG GCA AGTACAGGATCAGTTCCG
5'Hal3BamHI_2	AACTCCAAGAATTT <u>GGATCC</u>
3'Hal3HpaI_2	TTCATAACGATTTT <u>TGTTAAC</u>
5'Hal3H265AR	CGGGATCC <u>CAGACTACCT</u> CAAGATGATGGAAAATTG SS CGTGTTGTTTGGCGCTACAG
5'Hal3F268A	CGGGATCC <u>CAGACTACCT</u> CAAGATGATGGAAAATTGCACGTGTT GGCT GCGCTACAGGTTTCGTTATC